

Instability Analysis of Chilli in Major Producing States of India: Need for Technological and Policy Interventions to Stabilise Production

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Abstract

Chilli, as a commercial crop, is grown in various agro-climatic regions of the country. The major producing states include Andhra Pradesh, Telangana, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Odisha, and West Bengal, which account for more than 80% of the national production. The Instability in production will have an impact on chilli production, prices and the domestic market and exports, which will ultimately affect the farmer's income. In this context, instability analysis at the state level is attempted to analyse and understand the instability and variability of chilli production in major producing states in India. The data regarding area, production, and productivity were collected for major producing states from 2011 to 2025. The Cuddy-Della Valle Instability Index was used to estimate the instability in area, production, and productivity of chilli in India. At the national level, the instability index for the productivity of chilli was 13.24 per cent. The instability index was estimated for major producing states. It was found that the instability in productivity was 30.11 per cent in Andhra Pradesh and 22.41 per cent in Telangana. It is clearly revealed that the instability in productivity of these states was significantly higher compared to the instability at the national level (13.24 per cent). The instability in productivity was 15.18 per cent in Madhya Pradesh, which is a little higher than the national average. Conversely, in low productivity states in Karnataka, the instability is high (22.41 per cent), while it is low in Orissa (6.59 per cent), and West Bengal (8.63 per cent) was significantly lower compared to the national average. Thus, it is inevitable to stabilise chilli production in high-productivity states such as Andhra Pradesh and Telangana, and more thrust should be given to the states with low productivity and high instability through research and development strategy, technology intervention and enabling policy environment.

Keywords: Chilli, Instability Index, Productivity, States, Stable, Technology, Policy.

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Introduction

In the Indian spice basket, chilli is the major spice contributing 40-42 % by volume and 20-22 % by value to the total spices exported. This demonstrates the importance of chilli in the national economy and the Global chilli market. Indian Chilli production accounts for more than 40 per cent of the global chilli production. Chilli is cultivated across varied agro-climatic regions of India, with major producing states including Andhra Pradesh, Telangana, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Odisha and West Bengal in the country. The crop serves as a critical source of income for millions of small and marginal farmers and supports a wide range of allied activities such as processing, storage, transportation, and export marketing. Indian chillies are valued globally for their pungency, colour, and quality, which provide the country with a competitive advantage in the international spice trade. Despite India's dominant position in chilli production, the sector faces several challenges related to productivity, escalating cost of cultivation, labour shortage, price volatility, quality compliance, etc. Fluctuations in domestic and international prices, rising input costs, pest and disease incidence, and increasing quality and phytosanitary standards in importing countries have significant implications for farmers' profitability and export performance.

Data and Analytical Framework

The vigorous secondary data on the selected parameters of chilli were gathered from the Spice Board (www.indiaspices.com), Ministry of Industry and Commerce, Government of India. The national and state-level data regarding area, production, and productivity were collected for major producing states from 2011 to 2025 to analyse and understand the instability and variability of chilli production in major producing states of India.

Instability analysis

The Cuddy-Della Valle Instability Index was used to estimate the instability in area, production, and productivity of chilli in India. This index is a modification of the coefficient of variation (CV) to account for the trend that is commonly present in time series economic data. It is superior to another scale-dependent measure, such as Standard Deviation or Root Mean Square of the residuals (RMSE) obtained from the fitted trend lines of raw data and hence suitable for cross-comparison. The Cuddy-Della Instability Index is calculated as follows:

Cuddy-Della Valle Instability Index:

The instability index was analysed by employing the CDVI (Cuddy Della Valle Index) method developed by John Cuddy and Della Valle for measuring instability in time

series data (Cuddy and Della Valle, 1978). However, the coefficient of Variation measures instability, but it overestimates the level of it in time-series data. The Cuddy Della Valle index (CDVI) is calculated as follows:

$$\text{Cuddy - Della Valle Instability Index (CDVI)} = \text{CV} * \sqrt{1 - \text{adj R}^2}$$

The coefficient of variation (CV) is a statistical measure of data points' dispersion around the mean in a data series. The coefficient of variation is a useful statistic for assessing the degree of variation between two data series, even if the means are radically different. It indicates the ratio of the standard deviation to the mean.

$$\text{Where, C.V. = Coefficient of Variation} = \frac{\text{Standard deviation}}{\text{mean}} \times 100$$

$$\text{adj R}^2 = \text{Coefficient of determination}$$

In **time-series data**, the **CDVI** is chosen over the **simple CV** in analysing instability, particularly in cultivation areas, production, and productivity, since it corrects a key limitation of CV, that is, the presence of trend and a realistic measure of instability, as it is a more accurate estimate of fluctuations around the trend, as the researchers usually mean by instability.

Results and Discussion

Instability analysis of chilli production at the national level

The instability of chilli production and productivity in India was analysed and reported. The instability indices indicate that chilli growth performance in India is stable or unstable over the study period. The instability index for chilli area, production and productivity was analysed for the period from 2011-12 to 2024-25 and presented in Table 1 and Figure 1. In time-series data, the CDVI (Cuddy-Della Valle Index) was selected over the simple CV in analysing instability, particularly in area, production, and productivity. The instability in area and production was found to be 5.42 per cent and 8.34 per cent, respectively, while the instability indices for the productivity of chilli were 13.24 per cent. This indicates low instability in the area and production, but higher instability in productivity during the study period. The productivity variability was mostly due to erratic climatic conditions, heavy pest and disease incidence, a major part of chilli acreage was under rainfed conditions, the fluctuations in rainfall, low irrigation facilities, and the non-availability of high-yielding varieties would have led to fluctuations in productivity levels. The results are analogous to Pavani *et al.* (2025) regarding chilli production variability.

Table 1. Degree of instability in the area, production and productivity of chilli in India Pradesh in the years 2011-12 to 2024-25

Particulars	Area (000 ha)	Production (000 tonnes)	Productivity (kg/ha)
Mean	89.6	205.7	2200
SD	101	456	437
CV	13.57	24.91	18.96
CDVI	5.42	8.34	13.24

Figure 1. Instability index in the area, production and productivity of chilli in India from 2011-12 to 2024-25

State-level analysis of instability in chilli production landscape in India

Andhra Pradesh

The instability analysis of chilli production in Andhra Pradesh was analysed for the period from 2011-12 to 2024-25 and presented in Table 2. The CDVI for the area was found to be 19.79 per cent, while the instability index for the production and productivity of chilli was 30.11 per cent and 25.66 per cent, respectively. It indicates low instability in the area, but higher instability in production and productivity during the study period. The productivity variability was mostly due to erratic climatic conditions, heavy pest and disease incidence, a major part of the chilli area being in rainfed regions, fluctuations in rainfall, limited irrigation facilities, and the non-availability of high-yielding varieties. The results are analogous to Pavani *et al.* (2025) regarding chilli production variability.

Table 2. Degree of instability in the area, production and productivity of chilli in Andhra Pradesh from 2011-12 to 2024-25

Particulars	Area (000 ha)	Production (000 tonnes)	Productivity (kg/ha)
Mean	189	816	4329
SD	43	292	1144
CV	22.56	35.80	26.43
CDVI	19.79	30.11	25.26

Telangana

The instability analysis of chilli production in Telangana was analysed for the period from 2011-12 to 2024-25 and presented in Table 3. CDVI for the area was found to be 21.7 per cent, while the instability index for the production and productivity of chilli was 17.0 per cent and 15.4 per cent, respectively. It indicates low instability in the area, but higher instability in production and productivity during the study period. The productivity variability was mostly due to erratic climatic conditions, heavy pest and disease incidence, a major part of the chilli area was under rainfed regions, the fluctuations in rainfall, low irrigation facilities, and the non-availability of high-yielding varieties.

Table 3. Degree of instability in the area, production and productivity of chilli in Telangana from 2011-12 to 2024-25

Particulars	Area (000 ha)	Production (000 tonnes)	Productivity (kg/ha)
Mean	100	437	4301
Std D	35	186	881
CV	34.6	42.6	20.5
CDVI	21.7	17.0	15.4

Madhya Pradesh

The instability analysis of chilli production in Madhya Pradesh was analysed for the period from 2011-12 to 2024-25 and presented in Table 4. The CDVI for area and production was found to be 9.28 per cent and 10.58 per cent, respectively, while the instability index for the productivity of chilli was 15.18 per cent. It indicates low instability in the area and production, but higher instability in productivity during the study period. The unevenness in

productivity was generally due to unpredictable climatic conditions and the fluctuations in rainfall.

Table 4. Degree of instability in the area, production, and productivity of chilli in Madhya Pradesh during 2011-12 to 2024-25

Particulars	Area (000 ha)	Production (000 tonnes)	Productivity (kg/ha)
Mean	90	206	2201
SD	25.8	90.3	429.8
CV	28.81	43.89	19.53
CDVI	9.28	15.18	10.58

Karnataka

The instability analysis of chilli production in Karnataka was analysed for the period from 2011-12 to 2024-25 and presented in Table 5. The CDVI for area and production was found to be 28.42 per cent and 28.63 per cent, respectively, while the instability index for the productivity of chilli was 22.41 per cent. It indicates high instability in the area and production, but medium instability in productivity during the study period. The variability in area and production was mostly due to crop diversification in chilli-growing areas, price fluctuations, and unpredictable climatic conditions.

Table 5. Degree of instability in the area, production and productivity of chilli in Karnataka from 2011-12 to 2024-25

Particulars	Area (000 ha)	Production (000 tonnes)	Productivity (kg/ha)
Mean	120	159	1346
SD	40.0	55.1	309.2
CV	33.25	34.65	22.96
CDVI	28.42	28.63	22.41

Odisha

The instability analysis of chilli production in Odisha was analysed for the period from 2011-12 to 2024-25 and presented in Table 6. The CDVI for the area was found to be 2.09 per cent, indicating low variability in the area, while the instability index for the production and productivity of chilli was medium, i.e., 8.31 per cent and 6.59, respectively. It

indicates low variability in the area, but moderate variability in production and productivity during the study period.

Table 6. Degree of instability in the area, production and productivity of chilli in Odisha from 2011-12 to 2024-25

Particulars	Area (000 ha)	Production (000 tonnes)	Productivity (kg/ha)
Mean	73.5	73.8	1003
SD	1.7	8.5	110.0
CV	2.30	11.48	10.96
CDVI	2.09	8.31	6.59

West Bengal

The instability analysis of chilli production in West Bengal was analysed for the period from 2011-12 to 2024-25 and presented in Table 7. The CDVI for the area was found to be 15.50 per cent, indicating moderate variability in the area, while the instability index for the production was 23.26 per cent, and productivity was 8.63, respectively. It indicates high variability in production, while it is low in productivity during the study period.

Table 7. Degree of instability in the area, production and productivity of chilli in West Bengal from 2011-12 to 2024-25

Particulars	Area (000 ha)	Production (000 tonnes)	Productivity (kg/ha)
Mean	62	105	1677
SD	10.0	31.6	265.9
CV	16.16	30.16	15.86
CDVI	15.50	23.26	8.63

Conclusion and Policy Implications

India is the world's largest producer, consumer, and exporter of chilli, accounting for around 40% of the world's chilli production. This crop is a major source of income for farmers. Chilly is a high-value commercial crop, especially for small and marginal farmers. At the national level, the instability index for the productivity of chilli was 13.24 per cent. From the state-level analysis, it was found that the instability in productivity was 30.11 per

cent in Andhra Pradesh and 22.41 per cent in Telangana. It is clearly revealed that the instability in productivity of these states was significantly higher compared to the instability at the national level (13.24 per cent). The instability in productivity was 15.18 per cent in Madhya Pradesh, which is a little higher than the national average. Conversely, in low productivity states in Karnataka, the instability is high (22.41 per cent), while it is low in Orissa (6.59 per cent), and West Bengal (8.63 per cent) was significantly lower compared to the national average. Thus, it is inevitable to stabilize chilli production in high-productivity states such as Andhra Pradesh and Telangana, and more thrust should be given to the states with low productivity and high instability through research and development strategy, technology intervention and enabling policy environment for sustainable chilli production in the country.

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